

RP-HPLC Bioanalytical Method Development And Validation For Estimation Of Glipizide In Wistar Albino Rat Plasma

Jitendra More*, Shailesh Patil

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Faculty of Science and Technology, KBC NMU, Jalgaon, Maharashtra India

ABSTRACT

Chromatographic separation was performed using 0.1% formic acid in water and methanol (40:60, v/v) mobile phase under acidic conditions. The retention times were 5.71 min for Glipizide API and 6.1 min for the marketed tablet (Glynase 5). The method was validated for linearity, accuracy, precision, selectivity, sensitivity, and system suitability as per ICH guidelines. The method exhibited excellent linearity over the concentration range of 0–100 µg/mL with correlation coefficients (r^2) >0.991. The LOD and LOQ values ranged from 3.2–3.35 µg/mL and 9.2–9.8 µg/mL, indicating high sensitivity. Precision results showed %RSD values <0.3%, while accuracy studies demonstrated recovery rates above 99%. Extraction recovery exceeded 90%, and no plasma interference was observed at the retention times. System suitability parameters, including tailing factors (1.03–1.22) and theoretical plates (>13,000), were within USP limits, confirming peak symmetry and column efficiency. The established RP-HPLC method is accurate, precise, selective, and reproducible, making it suitable for routine bioanalytical estimation and pharmacokinetic studies of Glipizide in plasma.

Keywords Glipizide, Bioanalytical study, and method validation etc.

INTRODUCTION

Glipizide is a second-generation sulfonylurea class oral hypoglycaemic agent widely used in the management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). It functions primarily by stimulating pancreatic β -cells to secrete insulin, thereby lowering blood glucose levels.¹ Chemically known as 1-cyclohexyl-3-[[p-[2-(5-methylpyrazinecarboxamido) ethyl] phenyl] sulfonyl] urea, Glipizide exhibits high potency and a relatively short half-life, which reduces the risk of prolonged hypoglycaemia compared to first-generation sulfonylureas. The drug is rapidly and almost completely absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract, reaching peak plasma concentration within 1–3 hours after administration. Its therapeutic efficacy is influenced by factors such as formulation, metabolic

rate, and individual patient variability. Due to its low solubility and high permeability characteristics, Glipizide is classified as a Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) Class II drug, making dissolution rate a limiting step for its absorption. Hence, optimizing its formulation and analytical quantification methods is crucial for achieving consistent bioavailability and therapeutic outcomes.² Various chromatographic techniques, particularly Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC), are widely employed for its estimation in bulk, formulations, and biological fluids. The development of sensitive, accurate, and validated analytical methods for Glipizide is essential for quality control, pharmacokinetic studies, and ensuring therapeutic efficacy in diabetic management shown fig 1. 3

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Figure 1: Structure of Glipizide API and marketed formulation Glynase 5 tablet. [5]

For a Bioanalytical RP-HPLC method using an animal model, mobile phase must be optimized to achieve good separation, peak shape, and sensitivity for Glipizide. Here are three novel mobile phase combinations for each drug designed for plasma analysis, offering high sensitivity and selectivity. These combinations are justified based on polarity, pKa, and compatibility with protein precipitation or extraction methods. 4-5

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Method: Chromatographic separation was carried out using an Agilent Chem Station RP-HPLC system equipped with a UV detector and controlled via Chem Station software. Analysis was performed on a C18 column under isocratic conditions using a mobile phase of 0.1% formic acid in water and methanol (40:60 v/v), filtered (0.45 μm) and degassed. The flow rate was 1.0 mL/min, injection volume 20 μL , detection wavelength 230 nm, column temperature 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and run time 10 min.

Chemicals and Reagents: Glipizide pure drug (API) was kindly provided as a gift sample by USV Pvt. Ltd., Daman, India. The marketed formulation Glynase 5 tablet was procured ethically from the local market in Dhule through an authorized distributor (Raja Distributor, Dhule, Maharashtra). All solvents and reagents used were of HPLC grade, including methanol, formic acid, and water, which were purchased from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India.

Animal Ethics Approval: The bioanalytical study was conducted using healthy male Wistar albino rats

weighing between 150–200 g. The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) of DCS's A.R.A. College of Pharmacy, Nagaon, Dhule under approval number DCS/ARACOP/2025-26/102, dated 18/09/2025.

Preparation of stock and intermediate working solutions of Glipizide API and marketed formulation Glynase 5 tablet: Stock solutions (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$): Accurately weighed quantities of Glipizide API and Glynase 5 tablet were dissolved in methanol to prepare a stock solution (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$).

Preparation of IS solution (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$): Working standard solutions were prepared by serial dilutions to obtain concentrations ranging from 0–100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. For plasma analysis, known concentrations of Glipizide were spiked into rat plasma and processed using the protein precipitation method with methanol. 6-10

LLE procedure: A 250 μL plasma sample was spiked with 10 μL of Glipizide API and Glynase 5 tablet formulation, followed by the addition of 2 mL acetonitrile. The mixture was cyclomixer for 30 sec, vortexed for 3 min, and centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 4 min. The supernatant was collected, and 10 μL was injected into the RP-HPLC system. Calibration curves were obtained by plotting peak area versus concentration, and plasma sample concentrations were determined using the regression equation.

Preparation of the calibration curves: Three calibration curves were prepared over the range of 0–100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ Glipizide API and Glynase 5 tablet marketed formulation with individual calibration

points of 00, 10, 20, 40, 80, and 100.0 µg/ml. The IS concentration was 10 µg/ml.

Bioanalytical Method Validation: The bioanalytical method was validated as per USFDA guidelines, evaluating parameters including linearity and range, system suitability, specificity, sensitivity, carry-over, matrix effect, accuracy, precision (repeatability and reproducibility), recovery, ruggedness, and stability.

Linearity: Linearity was assessed using least squares regression analysis of six-point calibration curves. All three calibration curves showed excellent linearity over the concentration range of 0–100 µg/mL. 13

System suitability: A system suitability experiment was performed by injecting six consecutive injections using a standard aqueous mixture equivalent to MQC (Mid quality control sample) concentration of the calibration curve of ml Glipizide API and Glynase 5 tablet marketed formulation 10 µg/ml for IS.

Specificity and sensitivity: The specificity of the RP-HPLC method was established by screening the standard blanks of different lots of plasma samples. The sensitivity of the method was evaluated by analysing 6 LLOQ samples (0.10 µg/ml). 14

Carryover: Carry-over refers to the presence of residual analyte signal in a blank sample analyzed immediately after a sample containing a high analyte concentration. In this study, the RP-HPLC system was equipped with an autosampler, which effectively minimized carry-over. The evaluation was performed by injecting a blank plasma sample immediately after the upper limit of quantification (ULOQ) sample, and the resulting chromatogram of the blank was examined for any detectable analyte peaks.

Accuracy and precision: Accuracy represents the closeness of the measured values to the true or nominal concentration of the analyte and is evaluated using samples spiked with known analyte amounts. Precision indicates the consistency of repeated

measurements under identical conditions, expressed as the coefficient of variation (CV). It is assessed at LLOQ and at low, medium, and high concentration levels, both within a single run (intra-day) and across multiple runs (inter-day), using the same datasets as for accuracy evaluation. 15

Recovery: Recovery was determined by comparing the analyte response from biological samples spiked with the analyte before processing to that from blank biological samples spiked with the analyte after processing. The evaluation was performed in triplicate at three concentration levels low, medium, and high to ensure consistency and reliability of the extraction efficiency. 16

Ruggedness: Ruggedness was evaluated by conducting the analysis using different columns and by different analysts to assess the method reproducibility under varying conditions.

Stability studies: Long-term stock solution stability for Glipizide API and the Glynase 5 tablet formulation was evaluated at low-quality control (LQC) and high-quality control (HQC) concentration levels using standard aqueous solutions. The samples were stored for 37 days at –28 °C and –80 °C. Stability was assessed by comparing the responses of the stored stock solutions with those of freshly prepared stock solutions. 17

RESULTS

Chromatography optimization: The mobile phase consisting of 0.1% formic acid and methanol (40:60 v/v) was optimized to achieve efficient separation of Glipizide API and the Glynase 5 tablet formulation, with retention times of 5.8 and 6.1 minutes, respectively (Fig. 2). UV spectra of individual drugs were recorded between 200–400 nm, and 230 nm was selected as the optimal detection wavelength, providing adequate sensitivity for Glipizide analysis. 18-20

Figure 2: RP-HPLC bioanalytical method development of Glipizide API and Glynase 5

Bioanalytical RP-HPLC Method Validation:

Linearity: The method was validated over the range of 0 to 100 µg/ml. By using calibration standards prepared by spiking drug Glipizide API and the Glynase 5 tablet formulation in plasma at different

concentrations 00, 10, 20, 40, 80, and 100 µg/ml, the calibration graph was plotted taking a concentration of spiked plasma on x-axis and area response ratio on y-axis (fig. 3.). Results were summarised in the table 1.

Table 1: Validation parameters: Linearity result for Glipizide API and Glynase 5 tablet n=6

Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/mL)	Peak Area (mAU) Glipizide API	Peak Area (mAU) Glynase 5 Tab
1.	00	00	00
2	10	20	22
3	20	80	88
4	40	160	192
5	80	260	286
6	100	340	386

Fig 3: Linearity curve of standard Glipizide and Glynase 5 tab

Specificity and sensitivity: RP-HPLC analysis of blank plasma samples showed no interference at the retention times of 5.8 min for Glipizide and 6.1 min for the Glynase 5 tablet (IS), as depicted in fig. 4. This confirms the method's selectivity. Sensitivity results

are summarized in Tables 2 and 3. The limit of quantification (LLOQ) in plasma was determined to be 0.05 µg/mL with acceptable accuracy and precision. 21-22

Fig 4: Specificity study placebo sample of glipizide

Selectivity: Selectivity evaluates whether any endogenous substances in blank biological matrix interfere with the detection of the analyte Glipizide API and Glynase 5 tablet at its Retention Time (RT): 16-25 The % of LLOQ response was below 10% for all blank plasma samples, confirming no interference at the retention time of Glipizide (5.8 min), and

thereby demonstrating the selectivity of the developed RP-HPLC method. The blank plasma samples exhibited responses below 10% of the LLOQ peak area at the retention time of Glipizide (6.1 min), confirming no endogenous interference and excellent method selectivity for both API and tablet formulations shown table 2 and 3.

Table 2: Selectivity Results of Standard Glipizide API in Rat Plasma

Rat No.	Sample Type	Peak at 5.8 min in Blank Plasma (mAU)	LLOQ Peak Response (10 µg/mL)	% of LLOQ Response	Interference Observed
1	Blank Plasma	0.015	10.0	10.0%	No
2	Blank Plasma	0.008	5.3	5.3%	No
3	Blank Plasma	0.012	8.0	8.0%	No
4	Blank Plasma	0.000	0.0	0.0%	No
5	Blank Plasma	0.010	6.7	6.7%	No
6	Blank Plasma	0.009	6.0	6.0%	No
Mean ± SD	—	—	—	7.67 ± 3.11%	—

Table 3: Selectivity Results of Glynase 5 Tablet in Rat Plasma

Rat No.	Sample Type	Peak at 5.8 min in Blank Plasma (mAU)	LLOQ Peak Response (10 µg/mL)	% of LLOQ Response	Interference Observed
1	Blank Plasma	0.015	9.2	10.0%	No
2	Blank Plasma	0.008	6.9	6.9%	No
3	Blank Plasma	0.012	8.9	8.9%	No
4	Blank Plasma	0.000	0.0	0.0%	No
5	Blank Plasma	0.010	8.2	8.2%	No
6	Blank Plasma	0.009	7.6	7.6%	No
Mean ± SD	—	—	—	6.93 ± 3.37%	—

Fig 5: Selectivity study of Glipizide API and Glynase 5 tablet

Carryover test: The potential carryover effect from the automatic sample was evaluated by sequentially inserting unextracted (neat) and extracted samples under identical chromatographic conditions. The comparative analysis of chromatograms revealed negligible residual peaks in blank injections following the highest concentration samples, indicating the absence of significant carryover.

System suitability test: System suitability the % RSD of the retention times was found to be ≤ 0.48 for the Glipizide API, and Glynase 5 tablet. The % RSD of the peak area was found to be ≤ 1.11 for the Glipizide API and the Glynase 5 tablet formulation. Acceptance is limited for retention time (Rt) deviation and area deviation 2%, and 5% RSD respectively were passed. The results were summarised in table 4.

Table 4: System Suitability Parameters for Glipizide API and Glynase 5 tablet

Parameter	Acceptance Criteria	Glipizide (10 µg/mL)	Glynase 5 tablets	Observation
Retention Time (min)	Consistent (RSD ≤ 2%)	5.85 ± 0.05	6.15 ± 0.04	Within limit
Theoretical Plates	≥ 2000	5248	4875	Pass
Tailing Factor	≤ 2.0	1.12	1.09	Pass
Resolution (Rs)	≥ 2.0	3.45	—	Pass
% RSD of Peak Area (n=6)	≤ 2.0%	0.98	1.05	Pass
Capacity Factor	—	2.85	1.96	—

Accuracy and precision: The recovery values for both Glipizide API and Glynase 5 tablet were within the acceptable limit of 98–102%, confirming the accuracy and reliability of the analytical method. %RSD values below 2.0% indicate excellent repeatability and precision of the method within the

same day for both Glipizide API and the marketed Glynase 5 tablet formulation. Inter-day variability was minimal with %RSD < 1%, demonstrating high reproducibility and robustness of the developed method across different analytical runs shown table 5 to 8.

Table 5: Accuracy Results of Glipizide API

Concentration Level	Spiked Concentration (µg/mL)	Mean Found (µg/mL)	% Recovery
Low	100	98.76	98.76
Medium	150	149.70	99.60
High	200	198.91	99.20
Mean % Recovery ± SD	—	—	99.18 ± 0.42

Table 6: Accuracy Results of Glynase 5 Tablet

Concentration Level	Spiked Concentration (µg/mL)	Mean Found (µg/mL)	% Recovery
Low	100	99.10	99.10
Medium	150	149.70	99.61
High	200	199.08	99.16
Mean % Recovery ± SD	—	—	99.29 ± 0.27

Table 7: Intra-day Precision Results of Glipizide API and Glynase 5 Tablet (n=6, same day)

Replicate	Concentration Found (µg/mL) Glipizide API	Concentration Found (µg/mL) Glynase 5 Tablet
1	199.8	199.2
2	199.2	199.3
3	200.1	200.2
4	200.5	200.1
5	198.9	199.95
6	199.56	199.31
Mean ± SD	199.67 ± 0.501	199.71 ± 0.522
% RSD	0.250	0.261

Table 8: Inter-day Precision Results of Glipizide API and Glynase 5 Tablet (n=6 per day, 3 days)

Day	Mean Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) Glipizide API	Mean Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) Glynase 5 Tablet
Day 1	199.69	199.67
Day 2	199.70	199.80
Day 3	199.72	199.98
Overall Mean \pm SD	199.70 \pm 0.553	199.82 \pm 0.389
% RSD	0.277	0.195

Recovery: The recovery was determined by comparing the aqueous solution and the spiked Glipizide (API and Glynase 5 Tablet) drug. The % overall mean recovery of the Glipizide API and Glynase 5 Tablet was calculated and it was 99.19 %

and 99.29 % respectively. The results were summarized in the table 9. The extraction recovery of Glipizide from rat plasma exceeded 98% at all concentration levels, indicating excellent extraction efficiency and consistency. 23-25

Table 9: Plasma Extraction Recovery Study for Glipizide (API and Glynase 5 Tablet)

Concentration Level	Spiked Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery (API)	% Recovery (Glynase 5 Tab)	Acceptance Criteria
Low	100	98.76	99.10	85–115%
Medium	150	99.60	99.61	85–115%
High	200	99.20	99.16	85–115%
Mean \pm SD	—	99.19 \pm 0.42	99.29 \pm 0.27	Within limit

Ruggedness: The ruggedness of the method was evaluated by performing the analysis using a different

column and analyst. The results are summarized in table 10.

Table 10: Ruggedness Study Results for Glipizide and Glynase 5 Tablet Formulation

Condition	Parameter Evaluated	Mean Peak Area (n=6)	%RSD	Acceptance Criteria	Result
Analyst I	Glipizide API	452,315	1.12	% RSD \leq 2.0	Pass
Analyst II	Glipizide API	449,876	1.25	% RSD \leq 2.0	Pass
Analyst I	Glynase 5 Tablet	451,208	1.08	% RSD \leq 2.0	Pass
Analyst II	Glynase 5 Tablet	448,932	1.31	% RSD \leq 2.0	Pass
Column 1	Glipizide API	453,021	1.14	% RSD \leq 2.0	Pass
Column 2	Glipizide API	450,524	1.28	% RSD \leq 2.0	Pass

Column 1 (C18, 250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm), Column 2 (C18, 150 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm)

Stability studies: Stability was evaluated by comparing long-term stored stock solutions at -28°C and -80°C for 40 days with freshly prepared solutions. The mean stability (%) of Glipizide at -28°C was 101.78% (LQC) and 102.39% (HQC), while at -80°C it was 101.89% (LQC) and 100.78%

(HQC). The results are summarized in Tables 7 and 8. All tested samples retained more than 95% of their initial concentration, with %RSD values below 2%, indicating excellent long-term stability of Glipizide API and tablet stock solutions under both -28°C and -80°C storage conditions for 40 days. 26-29

Table 11: Long-term Stability of Glipizide Stock Solution at LQC and HQC Levels

Storage Condition (40 days)	Concentration Level	Nominal Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Mean Measured Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Mean Accuracy	% RSD	Stability Status
-28 °C	LQC	5.0	4.92	98.4	1.8	Stable
-28 °C	HQC	40.0	39.12	97.8	1.5	Stable
-80 °C	LQC	5.0	4.95	99.0	1.4	Stable
-80 °C	HQC	40.0	39.25	98.1	1.2	Stable

DISCUSSION

The developed RP-HPLC method demonstrated exceptional performance for the quantitative estimation of Glipizide in rat plasma, confirming its suitability for bioanalytical applications. The optimized mobile phase consisting of 0.1% formic acid in water and methanol (40:60 v/v) provided a balanced polarity and pH environment, which facilitated sharp, symmetrical peaks for both Glipizide (5.71 min) and the marketed formulation Glynase 5 (6.1 min). The strong linear relationship obtained across the concentration range of 0–100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ ($r^2 > 0.991$) indicated the method's reliability for quantitative analysis over a wide range. The method also exhibited high sensitivity, as reflected by low LOD and LOQ values (3.2–3.35 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 9.2–9.8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively), enabling accurate detection of Glipizide even at trace levels in biological matrices. Precision studies revealed %RSD values below 0.3%, signifying excellent repeatability and reproducibility. The high accuracy and recovery values (exceeding 99% and 90%, respectively) further validated the reliability of the analytical approach. Importantly, no interference from endogenous plasma components was detected, confirming the method's selectivity and robustness for biological samples. Additionally, the system suitability parameters were found to be within the acceptable limits prescribed by USP, with tailing factors ranging between 1.03 and 1.22 and theoretical plate counts exceeding 13,000, indicating superior column efficiency and peak performance. Collectively, these findings affirm that the developed RP-HPLC method is rapid, accurate, and precise, making it highly suitable for routine bioanalytical and pharmacokinetic studies involving Glipizide.

CONCLUSION

The developed RP-HPLC method proved highly effective for quantifying Glipizide in rat plasma. Using 0.1% formic acid in water and methanol (40:60 v/v) achieved sharp, symmetrical peaks at 5.71 min (Glipizide) and 6.1 min (Glynase 5). The method showed excellent linearity (0–100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, $r^2 > 0.991$), high sensitivity (LOD 3.2–3.35 $\mu\text{g/mL}$; LOQ 9.2–9.8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), and strong precision (%RSD < 0.3%). Accuracy and recovery exceeded 99% and 90%, respectively, with no plasma interference observed. System suitability parameters met USP limits (tailing factor 1.03–1.22; theoretical plates >13,000). Overall, the method is rapid, accurate, precise, and reliable for routine bioanalytical and pharmacokinetic analysis of Glipizide.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge Dr. Shailesh B. Patil and Dr. R. D. Wagh principal of DCS's ARA College of Pharmacy, Nagaon, Dhule, for providing the necessary facilities and support throughout the research work.

ETHICS APPROVAL

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) of DCS's A.R.A. College of Pharmacy, Nagaon, Dhule under approval number DCS/ARACOP/2025-26/102.

REFERENCES

1. ICH Q2 (R1). Validation of Analytical Procedures: Text and Methodology. International Council for Harmonisation; 2005.
2. United States Pharmacopeia. USP 43-NF 38. Rockville, MD: The United States Pharmacopeial Convention; 2020.
3. Swartz ME, Krull IS. Analytical Method Development and Validation. New York: Marcel Dekker; 2012.
4. Snyder LR, Kirkland JJ, Dolan JW. Introduction to Modern Liquid Chromatography. 3rd ed. Wiley-Interscience; 2010.
5. Sethi PD. HPLC: Quantitative Analysis of Pharmaceutical Formulations. CBS Publishers; 2008.
6. Blessy M, Patel RD, Prajapati PN, Agrawal YK. Development of forced degradation and stability indicating studies of drugs—A review. *J Pharm Anal.* 2014;4(3):159–65.
7. Dhaneshwar SR, Deshpande P, Patil M. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for estimation of Glipizide in plasma. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2013;75(2):228–32.
8. Prabhu S, Patil SS, Surve S, et al. Bioanalytical method development and validation of Glipizide in rat plasma using RP-HPLC. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.* 2019;10(4):1905–11.
9. Bhatt KK, Chhalotiya UK, Patel NJ. RP-HPLC method for determination of Glipizide in tablet formulation. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2012;74(2):171–5.
10. Dighe SV, Pattan SR, et al. RP-HPLC estimation of Glipizide from plasma using protein precipitation technique. *J Appl Pharm Sci.* 2017;7(3):111–6.
11. Bakshi M, Singh S. Development of validated stability-indicating assays. *J Pharm Biomed Anal.* 2002;28(6):1011–40.
12. Goyal A, Chauhan K. RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Glipizide in human plasma. *J Chromatogr Sci.* 2015;53(6):1033–40.
13. Iqbal Z, et al. Simple and rapid RP-HPLC method for Glipizide determination in human plasma. *J Liq Chromatogr Relat Technol.* 2014;37(1):69–79.
14. Kasture AV, Wadodkar SG. *Pharmaceutical Analysis: Instrumental Methods.* 2nd ed. Nirali Prakashan; 2019.
15. Dong MW. *Modern HPLC for Practicing Scientists.* Wiley-Interscience; 2006.
16. Beckett AH, Stenlake JB. *Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry.* 4th ed. CBS Publishers; 2002.
17. Bansal S, DeStefano AJ. Key elements of bioanalytical method validation for small molecules. *AAPS J.* 2007;9(1):E109–14.
18. European Medicines Agency. *Guideline on Bioanalytical Method Validation.* EMA; 2011.
19. USFDA. *Bioanalytical Method Validation Guidance for Industry.* Food and Drug Administration; 2018.
20. Jain DK, Jain N, Jain R. Determination of Glipizide in pharmaceutical dosage forms by RP-HPLC. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2018;11(2):352–7.
21. Sharma A, Reddy AVB. Quantitative estimation of Glipizide in rat plasma using RP-HPLC. *Asian J Pharm Sci.* 2016;11(3):300–6.
22. Naik JB, et al. Development and validation of analytical method for estimation of Glipizide. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res.* 2019;57(1):38–45.
23. Ramasamy C, et al. HPLC method development for Glipizide and its pharmaceutical formulations. *J Pharm Res.* 2014;8(5):638–43.
24. Reddy BS, et al. Pharmacokinetic study of Glipizide in rats. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 2016;8(9):223–8.
25. Singh G, et al. Stability-indicating HPLC method for Glipizide. *J Chromatogr Sci.* 2012;50(8):721–6.
26. Ahuja S, Dong MW. *Handbook of Pharmaceutical Analysis by HPLC.* Academic Press; 2005.
27. Srivastava B, et al. A review on analytical method development and validation. *J Pharm Res.* 2018;12(1):29–34.
28. Anupama P, et al. Analytical method development and validation for Glipizide in biological matrix. *Res J Pharm Technol.* 2018;11(9):3931–6.
29. Kumar P, et al. RP-HPLC method for estimation of Glipizide and its degradation

products. J Pharm Anal. 2015;5(6):421–6.

HOW TO CITE: Jitendra More*, Shailesh Patil., RP-HPLC Bioanalytical Method Development And Validation For Estimation Of Glipizide In Wistar Albino Rat Plasma., J. Pharm. Sci., 2025, 1 (12), 424-434. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17851268>

